

The Confluence of Language and Life: Whole-Person Learning in ESL Education

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Abstract

In this study, the use of whole-person learning in English as a Second Language (ESL) is perceived at different prospects of students-thinking, feelings, social interactions, and physical activities. It is tried to explore how whole-person learning is practiced, the problems faced, and what results come from using these methods in ESL settings are the prime concern of this study. The study collects data from interviews with ESL teachers, observations of classrooms, and stories collected from students to show how this different approach can help build language skills and support personal growth.

This research focuses on how whole-person learning is used in ESL programs and what effects it has on students' language skills, motivation, and personal growth. It considers how emotional understanding and cultural context can enhance ESL learning. By using whole-person methods, the article examines how such practices encourage learners to connect more with the language, improving skills and critical thinking.

With this, the research study states the application of the teaching methods for bringing students' sensory wellbeing, knowledge to respect culture, values and assumption and communal relation. It is to implement by integrating whole person learning with the theories underlying like Vygotsky's concept on social learning and Maslow theory of need hierarchy.

The research connects motivation, social learning, and school performance and gives practical ideas for ESL teachers to create friendly and adaptable classrooms.

Keywords: Whole-person, ESL classrooms, Multiple Intelligence, Holistic, Humanistic education, Interpersonal